

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING SOCIAL COMPETENCES OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes the pedagogical aspects and specific features of the formation of social competences of elementary school students.*

Keywords: *social competence, primary class, relational approach, specialization, indicators, basic criteria, comprehensive approach, components, skill, ability.*

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the reforms being implemented in our country is the growing up of the young generation as a morally mature, well-rounded, inquisitive, demanding and proactive social activist. In particular, the reforms implemented in the field of education are also important for the development of students and young people as socially active citizens. On June 15, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, in his speech at a meeting with public representatives dedicated to "Ensuring social stability, preserving the purity of our holy religion - the demand of the times", stated that the protection of citizens' rights in our republic, coordination of appeals of individuals and legal entities, and their interests "On Protection", as well as in the "solemn speech dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the role and importance of the Constitution in raising the legal consciousness and culture of our citizens and increasing their social and political activity is incomparable. It is not for nothing that it was specially mentioned¹.

It is important to increase the activity of students as socially active citizens in the Republic of Uzbekistan by forming basic competencies in education in accordance with their age characteristics, based on the continuity and integrity of education, the priority of the student's personality and interests. In particular, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 187 dated April 6, 2017 aims to provide knowledge by instilling general competencies related to the foundation and science, to form legal consciousness and legal thinking in them, to improve legal culture, and to form general competencies related to the science of jurisprudence in students. made it. In this decision, in order to increase the social activity of students, the formation of the competence of socially active citizenship in the student, the feeling of belonging to the events, phenomena and processes taking place in the society and active participation in them, to know one's civic duties and rights, to comply with them, to work and it is mentioned that it consists in forming the skills of dealing in civil relations and acquiring legal culture. In particular, if we focus on the concepts of competence, competence, civil competence, which are used as a separate concept in the development of pedagogic science, we should refer to the scientific opportunities in the work of local and foreign researchers. The word "Competence" comes from the word "to compete" and means "to compete", "to compete", "to compete".

Currently, the problem of developing social competence of elementary school students is an urgent social and pedagogical problem. Thus, in the conditions of modern socio-economic changes, the task of education is not only to provide a certain level of knowledge, skills and

qualifications on the basics of science, but also to ensure the ability to live in a modern, extremely complex society.

Achieving socially important goals, effective interaction and solving life problems. At the same time, primary school age is the most important stage in the development of a person, his socialization and the formation of social competence. Today, the school is called to become a factor in the development of a child's personality. The process of socialization of the young generation and its continuous development in new socio-cultural conditions is of fundamental importance in the science and practice of pedagogy.

MAIN PART

Taking into account the essence of social competence, many researchers define it as knowledge, abilities, skills, methods of behavior (models, templates, scenarios) in various areas of human social life.

N.A. Baranets defined the structure of social competence of junior schoolchildren and identified the following components in it:

- 1) motivational, including viewing another person as the highest value; manifestation of kindness, attention, help;
- 2) emotional related to emotional self-control;
- 3) to have means of organizing one's actions;
- 4) behavior, choosing appropriate communication methods for the situation, examples of morally valuable behavior.

One of the scientists of our republic, N.A. Muslimov, paying special attention to the etymological analysis of the concepts of "competent" and "competence", the concept of competence is not the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by the student, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. expressed as implying².

Since the introduction of the category of "competence" in the scientific works of foreign scientists, the foundations for the separation of the concepts of competence and competence have been created. But the emergence of the competent approach in general education is often associated with the name of the famous British psychologist Dj. Raven, who gave a detailed definition of competence in his work "Competence in Modern Society". In this scientific work, "a large number of components are formed, most of them are independent of each other, some components are more related to the cognitive sphere, and others - to the emotional sphere, these components are mutually effective as organizers of behavior. can fill in". Dj. Raven argues that "competence manifestations" are the essence of "motivated abilities". Thus, the psychological theory of competence was created by Dj. Raven, according to which competence is a product of the human psyche depending on biological heredity, abilities and other individual characteristics, and its development depends on the living environment (schools, families, work team, friends, etc.)³

At the modern stage of the development of the competent approach in education, attempts are made to clearly express the concepts of competence and competences that form a system. B. Gershunsky studied the concept of competence in relation to the professional field of human activity, which is "the level of professional education, experience and individual characteristics of a person, his motivational pursuit of continuous independent education and self-improvement, creativity and "responsible attitude". He considered professional competence as one of the

constituents of the structural link of the effectiveness of education consisting of literacy, education, professional competence, culture and mentality¹.

In the dictionary of pedagogy, the teacher's professional competence is defined as the acquisition of the necessary set of knowledge, skills and qualifications of the teacher, which determines the teacher's pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication and the formation of the teacher's personality as a carrier of certain values, ideals and pedagogical consciousness. is rified. Competence is the ability of the subject of activity to establish connections between knowledge and the situation, or in a broader sense, the actions necessary to solve the problem in a given situation, the guide of the process (knowledge + action). the ability to find the basis, to determine.

Defining the concept of "civic competence", its structure and the nomenclature of the competencies included in it is also a difficult task. The concept of the state standard of general secondary education is the development of human capital as one of the priorities of the state requirements in the field of general education - morally and spiritually mature, independent, active and competent living and working in a free democratic country in the conditions of the information society and market economy. aims to prepare the next generation of citizens.

General secondary education aims to explain legal concepts such as constitution, state, law, duty, obligation, citizen, human, law, ethics, manners, in the competence of having legal awareness, in the competence of having a legal consciousness, in the competence of social active citizenship in the state standard of general secondary education. . The competence to be legally cultured is legal skills, the reflex of compliance with the constitutional rights, duties and obligations of people and citizens is formed in the mind and thinking of students, the ability to make independent decisions in the implementation of rights and freedoms, legal interests. the competence to form a civil position is formed.

The author reveals the following features of the components of social competence:

1. Motivational component: children's ideas about the work of adults, the social importance of work, the need to protect the results of work; ideas about norms, rules of life in society expressed in the concepts of "possible", "impossible", "bad", "good", "necessary"; understanding the partner's mood based on the child's verbal and non-verbal characteristics; the child's understanding of the consequences of his and others' actions, their impact on the emotional state of other people;

2. Emotional component: the child's reaction to the emotional state of peers and adults; noble attitude, sensitivity, sympathy, partnership; the child's relationships with peers are built according to their wishes and interests; the ability to independently find solutions to conflicts and problematic situations;

3. Behavioral component: the child's ability to get the necessary information, to have a simple conversation with adults and peers, to interact in "child-child" and "child-adult" systems; the ability to participate in team work, participate in work tasks together with adults and provide assistance; the ability not to quarrel, to be calm in conflict situations.

The supplied components are N.A. Baranets, they are based on personal forms such as success motivation, volition, positive attitude towards oneself, high self-esteem, ability to act constructively in difficult situations.

Table 1. Laws of development of social competence in students

Criteria	Components	Indicators
Motivation	Relationships expressed through motives and values	The desire to express oneself in a socially approved activity, the dominance of motivation to achieve success, the value of creativity, a value-based attitude towards oneself and another person.
Knowing how to communicate effectively in society	Knowledge	Knowing the effective methods of interaction in the activity
Formation of orientation skills in the socio-cultural space	Social behavior skills and abilities	Emotional self-regulation skills, having the means to organize one's own behavior

Thus, the primary level is characterized by the formation of personal formations necessary for social adaptation at a low level. An unstable level is determined by a situation where certain indicators of social competence are sufficiently formed and can create a basis for achieving success in socially significant activities or relationships, while others are low. In this case, there may be different combinations of the level of formation of the components of social competence. A stable level implies the achievement of a stable development of personal development at all ages, which ensures success in social activities, i.e. high development rates of all components of social competence important for young people. Based on this, the social competence of a primary school student refers to the knowledge, abilities and skills that are sufficient to fulfill the obligations of a child that are characteristic of a certain period of life.

At the same time, the above definitions of the research show that the structure of social competence is primarily a set of social knowledge, skills and abilities used in the main areas of human activity. However, according to a number of scientists, the listed components of this competence structure can be supplemented with other less important components. Social competence of junior high school students is determined by the ability to know the rules and act in accordance with the rules. However, the interpretation of social competence as the ability to know and follow rules is not the only interpretation. Social competence is manifested in the desire and ability to communicate with other people.

CONCLUSION

At primary school age, children's social roles and functions change, their moral relations with the outside world and other people expand significantly; junior school age is sensitive for the formation of learning motives, development of stable cognitive needs and interests, assimilation of social norms and moral development, which is emphasized in many studies and this position is generally recognized; The system of needs for junior schoolchildren corresponds to their age. Creative play develops very well in school-age students. In these games, students begin to fully apply the knowledge, skills, and emotions they have received from the events, stories, books, and other sources they have heard and seen. From this point of view, we can see that it is important to work on the development of social competence of students in schools.

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